

3-Metallated Enamines VI⁺. Use as β -Oxo Vinyl Anion Equivalents

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Two possibilities to produce a synthetic equivalent for the β -oxo vinyl anion starting from a saturated carbonyl compound are investigated. In the first method, a methylthio group is introduced into the 3-position of the corresponding enamine. Metallation, regioselective attack by an electrophile followed by hydrolysis and oxidative elimination of the methylthio group completes the sequence. In the second method, the trimethyl silyl group is introduced instead. After deprotonation and regioselective reaction with an electrophile, the silylated enamine is chlorinated with N-chloro-succinimid. Dechlorosilylation and simultaneous hydrolysis of the enamine are achieved by means of trifluoro acetic acid/hydrochloric acid and sodium fluoride in ethanol.

WITHIN the last few years there has been growing interest²⁻¹⁸ in the generation of reagents for the β -oxo vinyl anion synthon II which, with one exception¹⁹ is not available directly. Heterosubstituted allylic anions²⁻⁶, vinyl anions⁷, allenic anions⁸⁻¹⁰, acetylenic anions¹¹ or deprotonated sulphones¹²⁻¹⁵, nitriles¹⁶, nitro compounds¹⁷ and phosphonium salts¹⁸ with a protected carbonyl group in the 3-position have been used as reagents for II. In no case a saturated carbonyl compound has been used as starting material to perform the transformation I \rightarrow III.

In the following paper we describe the realisation of this transformation, that is, the introduction of α,β -unsaturation along with electrophilic β -substitution into a saturated carbonyl compound in one reaction sequence.

Some years ago we showed the deprotonation of enamines like IV easily available from the carbonyl compound I to be possible to yield the 1-amino allyl

anion V²⁰⁻²³. Electrophilic introduction of a heteroatom X and subsequent deprotonation would yield 1,3-bis-heterosubstituted allyl anions VI very similar to those used as equivalents for II by other authors²⁻⁶ (Scheme 1). After electrophilic reaction and hydrolysis of the resulting enamine VII to ketone VIII the heteroatom X should be easily eliminated to yield the desired unsaturated carbonyl compound III.

We have investigated two heteroatoms-sulphur and silicon-within the proposed reaction sequence. This paper describes our first results on propiophenone as model compound.

3-Thiolated enamines: Propiophenone enamine IX, after deprotonation²⁰, can be γ -thiolated at -78° with dimethyldisulphide to give X in good yield. Reaction at 0° gave a mixture of IX, X and the γ -bis thiolated compound (XI: R=SCH₃). Further deprotonation of X and alkylation yielded the unstable enamines XI which are easily hydrolysed to ketones XII. The whole

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sequence starting with IX can be done in a "one-pot" reaction without isolation of any intermediate in high yield (73% XII b based on IX).

According to the well known elimination procedure^{24,25} XII is transformed to XIII.

Since a phenyl thio group can be more easily eliminated than a methyl thio group, we tried to introduce it by the reaction of IX with diphenyl disulphide. In this case, it is not possible to perform a clean mono thiolation even at -78°. On the other hand, reaction of the potassium salt of XIV or XV^{22,25} with dimethyldisulphide gave the monothiolated products, XVI a and XVI b respectively, but only together with starting material.

Scheme 3

Hence, the use of sulphur in the reaction sequence proposed in Scheme 1, though possible in principle, seems to be limited by the thiolation step of the deprotonated enamines of the type V.

3-Silylated enamines: We therefore did not continue these investigations but tried to use silicon for the same purpose, since silylation of deprotonated enamines is a clean, high yield reaction^{21,22,26}. For example, enamine IX is easily silylated to XVII (Scheme 4).

Scheme 4

Brominating hydrolysis, a well known enamine reaction, produces the ketone XVIII without any loss of

silicon. XVIII can be debromosilylated according to the procedure of Fleming²⁷ to obtain not the α -enone XIII a in this case but instead its ethanol adduct XIX in high yield.

After we had proved the transformation of 3-silylenamine into an α -enone to be possible, we investigated the reactivity of the key intermediate XVII. Deprotonation without any loss of silicon occurs smoothly. Although the bulky silyl group introduces large steric hindrance, a high regioselectivity has been achieved in alkylation reactions, even with a secondary bromide to yield the homologous 3-silylenamines XX. To transform these into the α -enones XIII the best procedure was to β -chlorinate with N-chlorosuccinimid to XXI and to hydrolyse with the two-phase system trifluoroacetic acid-ether/hydrochloric acid. Hydrolysis and partial dechlorosilylation can be done in one operation. Dechlorosilylation is completed by means of sodium fluoride.

Finally it should be pointed out that the whole sequence, starting with enamine IX can be done again in a "one pot" reaction without isolation of any intermediate in high yield as has been demonstrated for XIII b (82%) and c (87%).

Scheme 5

In the case of the isopropyl compound e the "one pot" reaction sequence yielded not the α -enone but the products XXII and XXIII as in Scheme 6. Obviously steric crowding in XXI e is a limiting factor for transformation to the α -enone.

Scheme 6

To conclude, 3-thiolated as well as 3-silylated enamines can be used as β -oxo vinyl anion equivalents. The latter seem to be more advantageous, mainly because they are better available. Further work in this field is in progress.

Experimental

The boiling points given refer to the temperature of a kugelrohr oven. According to the manufacturers it is 20° higher than the boiling point. The IR spectra were recorded with a Beckmann IR-4250 and a Perkin Elmer M 225 grating spectrophotometer and the values given are in cm^{-1} . The pmr (Jeol MNH-100) and ^{13}C -nmr (Varian CFT-20) spectra were taken in CDCl_3 with TMS as internal standard. The chemical shifts are in ppm. The notation s stands for singlet, d for doublet, t for triplet, q for quartet and m for multiplet. The ^{13}C -nmr spectral assignments were made with the help of "off-resonance spectra".

Preparation of starting materials: The compound IX was prepared according to the procedure used by Ahlbrecht and Rauchschalbe²⁰. For the preparation of XIV the method A of Ahlbrecht *et al.*²⁰ was used. XV was prepared according to the method used by Tweedie and Allabashi²¹. XVIII was prepared according to the method of Rauchschalbe²⁰.

1-N(Methylanilino)-1-phenyl-3-methylthio-prop-1-en (X): A 100 ml two-necked flask was evacuated and filled with argon. To IX (20 mmol, 4.46 g) in absolute tetrahydrofuran (30 ml)/TMEDA (3 ml) at 0° *n*-butyllithium in *n*-hexane (22 mmol, 1.5*N*) was added drop by drop using a syringe. After 2 hrs of stirring the deep red solution was cooled to -78° and dimethyl disulphide (22 mmol, 2.07 g) was added drop by drop. The solution turned pale green first and after 20 mins pale yellow. After 10 more mins of stirring it was allowed to warm up to room temperature, diluted with ether (20 ml) and the ether solution washed twice with water (20 ml). After drying with sodium sulfate the solvent was removed *in vacuo*. The product was purified by bulb to bulb distillation.

Yield=4.1 g (76%) pale yellow liquid. b.p. (bulb to bulb) (0.01 mm) 172°. Anal. Found: C, 75.50; H, 7.06; N, 5.16%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{19}\text{NS}$: C, 75.79; H, 7.11; N, 5.20%. IR (liquid): 1600, 1570, 1495, 1475, 1445, 1360, 1350, 1315, 1190, 1115, 1105, 990, 770, 750, 695, 510. δ : 1.98 (s, 3H, SCH_3); 3.06 (s, NCH_3); 3.12 (d, CH_2) together 5H; 5.96 (t, $J=8$ Hz, 1H, $=\text{C}-\text{H}$); 6.5-6.8 (m, 3H), 7-7.4 (m, 7H) aromatic. ^{13}C : 15.3 (q, SCH_3); 31.6 (t, CH_2); 38.2 (q, NCH_3); 112.5 (d, C_o , N-ph); 117.2 (d, C_p , N-ph); 122.7 (d, $=\text{C}-\text{H}$); 126.4 (d, C_o , C-ph); 128.0 (d, C_p , C-ph); 128.5 and 129.1 (d, C_m); 137.5 (s, C_i , C-ph); 145.1 (s, ph-C=); 147.9 (s, C_i , N-ph).

Preparation of XII: X (10 mmol, 2.69 g) was deprotonated according to the procedure given for IX and quenched with the corresponding alkyl iodide (11 mmol). Since compounds XI decompose during distillation, they were hydrolyzed by dissolving the crude products in ether (25 ml)/2NHCl (25 ml) and refluxing for 6 hrs with stirring. The ether layer was separated and the aqueous phase extracted twice with methylene chloride (10 ml). The combined organic

phases were washed with water (10 ml), dried with anhydrous sodium sulfate and the solvent removed *in vacuo*. The products were purified by bulb to bulb distillation.

1-Phenyl-3-methylthio-propan-1-on (XIIa): From IX. Yield: 1.55 g (86%) pale yellow liquid. b.p. (bulb to bulb) (0.01 mm)=130°. Anal. Found: C, 66.77; H, 6.72%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{OS}$: C, 66.63; H, 6.71%. IR (liquid): 2960, 2915, 1685, 1595, 1580, 1445, 1425, 1410, 1350, 1320, 1300, 1250, 1230, 1195, 1180, 1000, 970, 955, 755, 735, 690. δ : 2.05 (s, 3H, SCH_3); 2.81 (m, 2H, CH_2 -S); 3.12 (m, 2H, $\text{O}=\text{C}-\text{CH}_2$); 7.3-7.6 (m, 3H) and 7.9-8.1 (m, 2H) aromatic. ^{13}C : 15.8 (q, SCH_3); 28.5 (t, CH_2 -S); 38.6 (t, $\text{O}=\text{C}-\text{CH}_2$); 128.0 and 128.6 (d, C_o/C_m); 133.1 (d, C_p); 136.7 (s, C_i); 198.0 (s, $\text{O}=\text{C}$).

1-Phenyl-3-methylthio-butan-1-on (XII b): From X. Yield: 1.38 g (71%). From IX in a one pot reaction after deprotonation of *in situ* generated X at -78°. Yield: 1.94 g (100%) crude. Colourless liquid. b.p. (bulb to bulb) (0.01 mm)=90°. Anal. Found: C, 68.63; H, 7.26%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{OS}$: C, 68.00; H, 7.26%. IR (liquid): 2960, 2910, 1680, 1595, 1575, 1440, 1350, 1300, 1280, 1230, 1215, 1075, 995, 990, 750, 685. δ : 1.37 (d, $J=6$ Hz, 3H, CH_3); 2.13 (s, 3H, SCH_3); 2.92-3.45 (m, 3H, CH_2 and CH); 7.3-7.6 (m, 3H) and 7.9-8.1 (m, 2H) aromatic. ^{13}C : 13.6 (q, CH_3); 21.0 (q, SCH_3); 36.7 (d, CH); 45.6 (t, CH_2); 128.0 and 128.6 (d, C_o , C_m); 133.0 (d, C_p); 137.0 (s, C_i); 197.7 ($\text{O}=\text{C}$).

1-Phenyl-3-methylthio-pentan-1-on (XII c): From X. Yield=1.67 g (80%). From IX in a one pot reaction after deprotonation of *in situ* generated X at -78°. Yield: 2.08 (100%) crude. Colourless liquid. b.p. (bulb to bulb) (0.01 mm)=110°. Anal. Found: C, 70.03; H, 7.78%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{16}\text{OS}$: C, 69.19; H, 7.74%. IR (liquid): 2965, 2935, 2920, 2875, 1685, 1600, 1580, 1450, 1405, 1375, 1355, 1340, 1300, 1175, 1165, 1125, 1110, 1080, 1010, 1000, 975, 750, 690. δ : 1.02 (t, $J=8$ Hz, 3H, CH_3); 1.48-1.80 (m, 2H, CH_2 , broad); 2.04 (s, 3H, SCH_3); 3.21 (m, $\text{O}=\text{C}-\text{CH}_2$ and CH); 7.3-7.6 (m, 3H) and 7.9-8.1 (m, 2H) aromatic. ^{13}C : 11.3 (q, CH_3); 13.4 (q, SCH_3); 27.3 (t, CH_2); 43.7 (d, CH); 43.9 (t, $\text{O}=\text{C}-\text{CH}_2$); 128.0 and 128.6 (d, C_o , C_m); 133.0 (d, C_p); 137.2 (s, C_i); 197.8 (s, $\text{O}=\text{C}$).

Preparation of unsaturated ketones XIII from the ketosulphides XII: 20 mmol of either XII b or XII c were dissolved in 50 ml methanol. To this solution, a solution of 22 mmol sodium meta-periodate in 50 ml distilled water was added and the mixture was stirred for 6 hrs at room temperature under argon. Subsequently, 50 ml methylene chloride were added to it and the mixture stirred again for 10 mins. The precipitated sodium iodate was filtered off quickly on a Büchner funnel and the methylene chloride phase was dried with anhydrous potassium carbonate under argon. The solvent was removed under vacuum. The raw product was purified by bulb to bulb distillation under vacuum to obtain the corresponding unsaturated ketone.

(E)-1-Phenyl-but-2-en-1-on ‡ (XIII b): Yield=2.16 g (74%). Yellow liquid (impure). b.p. (bulb to bulb) (0.01 mm)=70°. IR (liquid): 2970, 2940, 1675, 1650,

‡ Known Compound. See Beilstein 3, Bd., VII, 1410 and K. R. BHARUCHA, *J. Chem. Soc. London*, 1956, 2446, but no spectral values given.

1630, 1600, 1585, 1455, 1335, 1300, 1225, 1140, 1040, 1025, 965, 955, 920, 760, 750, 695. δ : 1.95 (d, $J=6$ Hz, CH_3); 6.86-7.34 (ABX₂-system, $J_{AB}=16$ Hz, vinyl protons); 7.4-7.6 (m, 3H) and 7.9-8.1 (m, 2H) aromatic. ^{13}C : 18.6 (CH_3); 127.6 (OC-C=); 128.5 (C_o , C_m); 132.6 (C_p); 138.0 (C_i); 145.0 (=C-); 190.7 (C=O).

(*E*)-1-Phenyl-pent-2-en-1-ol (XIII c): Yield: 1.9 g (59%). Pale yellow liquid (impure). b.p (bulb to bulb) (0.01 mm)=150°. IR (liquid): 1675, 1655, 1625, 1600, 1580, 1450, 1425, 1350, 1295, 1285, 1255, 1220, 1180, 1005, 995, 980, 825, 790, 760, 735, 695, 665. δ : 1.12 (t, $J=7.5$ Hz, CH_3); 2.31 (d/q, $J=6.0/7.5$ Hz, CH_2); 6.82-7.30 (ABX₂ system, $J_{AB}=15.5$ Hz, vinyl protons); 7.4-7.6 (m, 3H) and 7.9-8.1 (m, 2H) aromatic. The structure was confirmed by a double resonance experiment. Irradiation at 2.3 ppm produces a neat AB-system at about 7 ppm, irradiation at 7.2 ppm produces a neat q at 2.3 ppm. ^{13}C : 12.4 (CH_3); 25.9 (CH_2); 125.0 (O=C-C=); 128.6 (C_o , C_m); 132.6 (C_p); 151.3 (=C-C); 191.1 (C=O).

Preparation of XVI from XIV or XV: XIV (10 mmol, 1.61 g) or XV (10 mmol, 1.47 g) and then petrol ether (30-50°) (30 ml) were added to a two necked flask filled with argon and containing 11 mmol dried potassium tertiary butoxide. The slurry was cooled to 0° and tertiary butyl lithium in *n*-hexane (11 mmol, 1.5N) was added drop by drop with stirring. After 3 hrs dimethylsulphide (11 mmol, 1.04 g) was added and after 15 mins at 0° and 15 mins at rt the slurry was diluted with ether (30 ml), washed twice with water saturated with NH_4Cl (20 ml), the ether phase dried with anhydrous sodium sulfate, the ether removed and the crude product purified by bulb to bulb distillation.

1-N (Methylanilino)-3-methylthio-2-methyl-prop-1-en (XVI a): From XIV. Yield: 1.06 g (51%) pale yellow liquid. *E*: *Z* = 75: 25%. b.p (bulb to bulb) (0.01 mm)=120°. Anal. Found: C, 69.47; H, 8.32; N, 6.65%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{17}\text{NS}$: C, 69.51; H, 8.26; N, 6.76%. IR (liquid): 2940, 2920, 1665, 1600, 1580, 1500, 1475, 1435, 1340, 1305, 1250, 1240, 1210, 1190, 1120, 1035, 750, 695. δ : *E*-isomer: 1.82 (d, $J=1.8$ Hz, CH_3); 1.93 (s, SCH_3); 3.02 (s, NCH_3); 3.18 (s, broad, CH_2). *Z*-isomer: 1.72 (d, $J=1.2$ Hz, CH_3); 1.98 (s, SCH_3); 3.04 (s, NCH_3); 3.14 (s, broad, CH_2) for both isomers: 5.95 (s, broad, vinyl protons); 6.6-7.2 (m, 3H) and 7.1-7.4 (m, 2H) aromatic. ^{13}C : *E*-isomer: 15.3 (q, SCH_3); 18.5 (q, CH_3); 34.91 (t, CH_2); 39.3 (q, NCH_3); 113.2 (d, C_o); 117.9 (d, C_p); 127.3 (s, =C- CH_3); 132.1 (d, C=C- CH_3); 148.5 (s, C_i); *Z*-isomer: 14.2 (q, SCH_3); 21.2 (CH_3); 31.4 (CH_2); 40.6 (NCH_3).

1-N (Methylanilino)-3-methylthio-prop-1-en (XVI b): From XV. Yield: 1.3 g (67%) pale yellow liquid. b.p (bulb to bulb) (0.01 mm)=90°. Anal. Found: C, 68.82; H, 8.82; N, 7.27%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{16}\text{NS}$: C, 68.35; H, 7.82; N, 7.25%. IR (liquid): 2920, 1650, 1600, 1505, 1370, 1335, 1275, 1265, 1230, 1125, 1035, 1000, 990, 940, 755, 695. δ : 2.04 (s, 3H, SCH_3); 3.10 (s, 3H, NCH_3); 3.22 (d/d, $J=8/1$ Hz, 2H, CH_2); 4.65 (d/t,

$J=14/8$ Hz, 1H, =CH-C); 6.74 (d, $J=14$ Hz, 1H, N-HC=); 6.8-7.1 (m, 3H) and 7.2-7.4 (m, 2H), aromatic. ^{13}C : 14.3 (SCH_3); 35.2 (CH_2); 35.3 (NCH_3); 98.7 (=C-C); 117.0 (C_o); 120.6 (C_p); 129.2 (C_m); 135.6 (N-C=C); 147.5 (C_i).

1-N (Methylanilino)-1-phenyl-3(trimethylsilyl)-prop-1-en (XVII): According to the procedure of Rauchschalbe²⁰ *n*-butyl lithium in hexane (44 mmol, 1.4 N) was added to IX (40 mmol, 8.9 g) dissolved in absolute THF (40 ml)/HMPT (2 ml) at 0° drop by drop using a syringe. After 2 hrs of stirring trimethyl silyl chloride (44 mmol, 4.8 g) was added dropwise. The solution was stirred for 1 hr and diluted with water (50 ml). Ether (20 ml) was added and the organic layer was washed twice with water (20 ml). After drying with sodium sulfate, the ether was removed and the crude XVII purified by bulb to bulb distillation. Yield: 9.4 g (80%) pale yellow liquid. b.p (bulb to bulb) (0.01 mm)=90°. Anal. Found: C, 77.02; H, 8.52; N, 4.41%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{26}\text{NSi}$: C, 77.23; H, 8.53 and N, 4.74%. IR: 1595, 1500, 1355, 1245, 855, 835, 765, 725, 690. δ : 0.05 [s, 9H, Si(CH_3)₃]; 1.55 (d, $J=8.5$ Hz, 2H, CH_2); 3.05 (s, 3H, NCH_3); 4.95 (t, $J=8.5$ Hz, 1H, =CH); 6.5-6.8 (m, 3H) and 7-7.4 (m, 7H) aromatic. ^{13}C : -1.3 [q, Si(CH_3)₃]; 19.6 (t, CH_2); 37.9 (q, NCH_3); 112.1 (d, C_o , N-ph); 116.4 (d, C_p , N-ph); 124.3 (d, =C-H); 125.8 (d, C_o , C-ph); 127.0 (d, C_p , C-ph); 128.4 and 128.7 (d, C_m); 138.8 (s, C_i , C-ph); 141.4 (s, N-C=); 147.9 (s, C_i , N-ph).

1-Phenyl-2-brom-3(trimethylsilyl)-propan-1-on (XVIII): XVII (9 mmol, 2.7 g) was dissolved in absolute CCl_4 (50 ml) and cooled to 0°. Argon was passed through the solution and Br_2 (10 mmol, 1.6 g) in CCl_4 (20 ml) added. After stirring for 10 mins in an argon atmosphere, 25 ml of a mixture of ice and water was added and again stirred at rt for 1 hr. The CCl_4 phase was washed twice with iced water, separated and CCl_4 removed with a Büchi evaporator. The residue was subsequently purified by bulb to bulb distillation. Yield: 1.8 g (63%) colourless liquid. b.p (bulb to bulb) (0.01 mm)=120°. Anal. Found: C, 51.58; H, 5.97%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{17}\text{BrOSi}$: C, 50.52; H, 6.01%. IR (liquid): 2960, 2900, 1680, 1600, 1585, 1450, 1405, 1355, 1250, 1195, 1185, 1150, 1055, 960, 855, 805, 765, 750, 715, 685. δ : 0.0 [s, Si(CH_3)₃]; 1.48 (d/d, $J=14/4.75$ Hz, 1H) and 2.01 (d/d, $J=14/10.5$ Hz; 1H) diastereotopic CH_2 ; 5.4 (d/d, $J=10.5/4.75$ Hz, 1H, CH); 7-7.5 (m, 3H) and 7.8-8.1 (m, 2H) aromatic. ^{13}C : -1.0 (q, Si- CH_3); 23.4 (t, CH_2); 46.1 (d, CH); 128.7 (d, C_m , C_o); 133.3 (d, C_p); 134.1 (s, C_i); 192.4 (s, O=C).

Preparation of 1-phenyl-3(ethoxy)-propan-1-on (XIX)²¹: XVIII (5 mmol, 1.4 g) was dissolved in 50 ml ethanol and a solution of NaHCO_3 (25 mmol, 2.1 g) in aqueous ethanol (30 ml) was added to it. The mixture was refluxed for 2 1/2 hrs, filtered, the filtrate washed twice with 10 ml portions of ethanol and the solvent removed with a Büchi evaporator. The raw product was distilled twice. Yield: 0.74 g (83%, GC-purity 93.2%), pale yellow liquid. b.p (bulb to bulb) (0.01 mm)=

‡ Known Compound. See Beilstein 3. Bd., VII, 1431 and E. BINARY, *Chem. Ber.*, 1931, 64, 2543, but not spectroscopically characterized.

≠ Known Compound. See: T. MATSUMOTO, T. NISHIDA and H. SEIRAHAMA, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, 27, 79.

85°. No satisfactory elemental analysis. IR (liquid): 2980, 2870, 1685, 1595, 1445, 1380, 1360, 1215, 1115, 745, 690. $H\delta$: 0.63 (t, $J=7$ Hz, 3H, CH_3); 2.68 (t, $J=6.5$ Hz, 2H, CH_2); 2.94 (q, $J=7$ Hz, 2H, $-O-CH_2$); 3.34 (t, $J=6.5$ Hz, 2H, $O-CH_2$); 6.8-7.2 (m, 3H) and 7.4-7.7 (m, 2H) aromatic. $^{13}C\delta$: 15.1 (q, $-CH_3$); 39.0 (t, $O=C-CH_2$); 65.8 and 66.5 (t, $O-CH_2$); 128.2 and 128.6 (d, C_o , C_m); 133.1 (d, C_p); 136.1 (s, C_t); 198.4 (s, $O=C$).

General procedure for the preparation of XX: XVII (10 mmol, 2.96 g) was deprotonated according to the procedure given for XVII and quenched with the corresponding alkyl halide. A minor set of signals in the ^{13}C -spectra of XXa-d is indicative for the presence of about 10% of the *E*-isomer.

Z-1-N-(Methylanilino)-1-phenyl-3-trimethylsilyl-but-1-en (XXa): Quenched with methyl iodide. Yield: 2.5 g (81%) pale orange liquid. b.p (bulb to bulb) (0.01 mm) = 115°. Anal. Found: C, 77.98; H, 8.78; N, 4.51%. Calcd. for $C_{20}H_{27}NSi$: C, 77.61; H, 8.79; N, 4.53%. IR (liquid): 2950, 1600, 1500, 1475, 1445, 1375, 1320, 1245, 850, 835, 770, 745, 695. $H\delta$: 0.00 [s, 9H, $Si(CH_3)_3$]; 0.94 (d, $J=7$ Hz, 3H, $C-CH_3$); 1.78 (d/q, $J=12/7$ Hz, 1H, CH); 2.90 (s, 3H, NCH_3); 5.63 (d, $J=12$ Hz, 1H, =CH); 6.3-6.7 (m, 3H) and 6.8-7.3 (m, 7H) aromatic. $^{13}C\delta$: -3.0 (q, $Si-CH_3$); 13.9 (q, $-CH_3$); 23.2 (d, -CH); 38.3 (q, NCH_3); 112.3 (d, C_o , N-ph); 116.6 (d, C_p , N-ph); 126 and 127.1 (d, =C-H, C_o , C-ph); 128.5 and 129 (d, C_m); 131.5 (d, C_o , C-ph); 139.0 (s, C_t); 140.4 (s, $N-C=$); 148.3 (s, C_t , N-ph).

Z-1-N-(Methylanilino)-1-phenyl-3-trimethylsilyl-pent-1-en (XXb): Quenched with ethyl iodide. Yield: 2.78 g (86%), pale yellow liquid. Anal. Found: C, 77.97; H, 9.05; N, 4.27%. Calcd. for $C_{21}H_{29}NSi$: C, 77.96; H, 9.04; N, 4.32%. IR (liquid): 2860, 1600, 1500, 1365, 1250, 855, 840, 770, 750, 695. $H\delta$: 0.00 [s, 9H, $Si(CH_3)_3$, 9H]; 0.85 (t, $J=7$ Hz, 3H, $-CH_2$); 1.27-1.91 (m, 3H, $-CH_2-$ and $-CH-$); 3.05 (s, 3H, NCH_3); 5.85 (d, $J=12$ Hz, 1H, =C-H); 6.6-6.8 (m, 3H) and 6.9-7.4 (m, 7H) aromatic. $^{13}C\delta$: -2.1 (q, $Si-CH_3$); 15.0 (q, $-CH_3$); 23.5 (t, CH_2); 31.1 (d, CH); 38.8 (q, NCH_3); 112.9 (d, C_o , N-ph); 116.7 (C_p , N-ph); 125.9 (d, C_o , C-ph); 127.0 (d, =C-); 128.4 and 128.8 (d, C_m); 130.3 (d, C_p , C-ph); 139.1 (s, C_t , C-ph); 141.6 (s, $ph-C=$); 148.3 (s, C_t , N-ph).

1-N-(Methylanilino)-1-phenyl-3-trimethylsilyl-hexa-1,5-dien (XXc): Quenched with allyl bromide. Yield: 2.45 g (73%), pale yellow liquid. b.p (bulb to bulb) (0.01 mm) = 135°. Anal. Found: C, 78.64; H, 8.68; N, 4.29%. Calcd. for $C_{22}H_{29}NSi$: C, 78.74; H, 8.71; N, 4.17%. IR (liquid): 2960, 2900, 1600, 1500, 1480, 1445, 1365, 1320, 1260, 1250, 995, 910, 845 (broad), 770, 750, 695. $H\delta$: 0.0 [s, 9H, $Si(CH_3)_3$]; 1.8-2.4 (m, 3H, CH, CH_2); 3.06 (s, 3H, NCH_3); 4.8-5.1 (m, 2H, = CH_2); 5.5-5.9 (m, 2H, =CH); 6.6-7.4 (m, 10H, arom.). $^{13}C\delta$: -2.1 (q, $Si-CH_3$); 29.4 (d, H-C); 34.9 (t, CH_2); 38.7 (q, NCH_3); 113.0 (d, C_o , N-ph); 114.8 (t, = CH_2); 116.8 (d, C_p , N-ph); 126.0 (d, C_o , C-ph); 127.1 (d, =CH-C); 128.4 and 128.8 (d, C_m); 129.2 (d, C_p , C-ph); 138.8 (d, $CH=CH_2$); 139.0 (C_t , C-ph); 141.5 (s, $Ph-C=$); 148.1 (s, C_t , N-ph).

1-N-(Methylanilino)-1-phenyl-4-methyl-3-trimethylsilyl-pent-1-en (XXd): Quenched with isopropyl bromide. Yield: 2.2 g (65%). Pink liquid. b.p (bulb to bulb) (0.01 mm) = 135°. Anal. Found: C, 78.21; H, 9.27; N, 4.12%. Calcd. for $C_{22}H_{29}NSi$: C, 78.27; H, 9.26; N, 4.15%. IR (liquid): 2960, 2900, 2880, 1600, 1500, 1480, 1450, 1365, 1335, 1320, 1300, 1260, 1250, 845, 770, 750, 695. $H\delta$: 0.06 [s, 9H, $Si(CH_3)_3$]; 0.92 and 0.95 (d, $J=7$ Hz) (total 6H, diastereotopic iso-propyl); 1.8-2.2 (m, 2H, CH); 3.12 (s, 3H, NCH_3); 6.02 (d, $J=12$ Hz, =C-H); 6.63-7.33 (m, 10H, aromatic). $^{13}C\delta$: -0.7 (q, $Si-CH_3$); 21.8 and 24.2 (q, diastereotopic CH_3); 29.7 (d, CH); 36.3 (d, CH-Si); 39.2 (q, NCH_3); 113.3 (d, C_o , N-ph); 116.7 (C_p , N-ph); 126.0 (d, C_o , C-ph); 127.8 (d, =C-H); 128.2 (d, C_p , C-ph); 128.4 and 128.7 (d, C_m); 129.3 (d, C_o , C-ph); 141.8 (s, $ph-C=$); 148.5 (s, C_t , N-ph).

1-N-(Methylanilino)-1-phenyl-2-chloro-3-trimethylsilyl-but-1-en (XX1b): A solution of XXa (10 mmol, 3.1 g) in absolute CCl_4 (25 ml) was stirred with N-chlorosuccinimid (12 mmol, 1.6 g) at rt for 5 hrs. The succinimid that formed was filtered off and the solvent removed *in vacuo* to yield crude XX1a. It was purified by bulb to bulb distillation under vacuum. Yield: 3.1 g (91%). Yellow liquid. b.p. (bulb to bulb) (0.01 mm) = 150°. Anal. Found: C, 70.19; H, 7.44; N, 4.04%. Calcd. for $C_{20}H_{26}NClSi$: C, 69.84; H, 7.62 and N, 4.07%. IR (liquid): 2960, 1600, 1495, 1345, 1245, 840 (broad), 745, 695, 690. $H\delta$: two sets of signals indicating two isomers in the ratio = 77:23 (min)%. 0.07 and 0.09 (min) (s, $SiCH_3$); 1.09 (min) and 1.25 (d, $J=6.8/7.0$ Hz, CH_2); 2.42 (min) and 2.51 (q, $J=6.8/7.0$ Hz, CH); 2.87 (min) and 3.09 (s, $N-CH_3$); 6.6-7.0 (m, 3H) and 7.1-7.6 (m, 7H). $^{13}C\delta$: -1.92 (q, $SiCH_3$); 14.5 (q, CH_2); 28.7 (d, CH); 37.9 (q, $N-CH_3$); 112.9 (min) and 113.2 (d, C_o , N-ph); 117.2 and 117.6 (min) (d, C_p , N-ph); signals at 127.8, 128.3, 128.8, 129.5 (d) and 137.7, 137.9, 139.2 (s) are crowded together, cannot be assigned; 147.2 (s, C_t , N-ph).

1-N-(Methylanilino)-1-phenyl-2-chloro-3-trimethylsilyl-pent-1-en (XX1c): A solution of XXb (10 mmol, 3.2 g) in absolute CCl_4 (25 ml) was stirred with N-chlorosuccinimid (15 mmol, 2.0 g) and 0.2 g α , α' -azoisobutyronitril for 14 hrs at rt. The succinimid formed was filtered off, the solvent removed *in vacuo* to yield XX1b. The product was purified by careful bulb to bulb distillation. Yield = 2.97 g (83%) pale yellow liquid. b.p. (bulb to bulb) (0.01 mm) = 120°. Anal. Found: C, 70.98, H, 7.89; N, 3.85%. Calcd. for $C_{21}H_{28}NClSi$: C, 70.45; H, 7.88 and N, 3.91%. IR (liquid): 2960, 1595, 1495, 1340, 1250, 1120, 855, 835, 745 and 695. $H\delta$: two sets of signals indicating two isomers in the ratio = 85 : 15 (min)%. 0.1 [s, 9H, $Si(CH_3)_3$]; 0.72 (min) and 0.88 (t, $J=7/7$ Hz, 3H, CH_2); 1.2-2 (m, 2H, CH_2); 2.28 (min) and 2.36 (d/d, $J=6/8.5$ and $4/12$ Hz, 1H, CH); 2.88 (min) and 3.12 (s, 3H, NCH_3); 6.5-6.9 (m, 3H) and 7.1-7.4 (m, 7H) aromatic. $^{13}C\delta$: -1.7 (q, $Si-CH_3$); 14.1 (q, CH_2); 21.8 (t, CH_2); 36.0 (d, CH); 38.3 (q, NCH_3); 113.3 and 113.5 (min) (d, C_o , N-ph); 117.2 and 117.7 (min) (d, C_p , N-ph); signals at 127.6, 128.1, 128.8, 129.3 (d) and 137.9, 138.1, 138.8 (s) are crowded together and cannot be assigned; 147.2 (s, C_t , N-ph).

i-N(Methylanilino)-1-phenyl-2-chloro-3-trimethylsilyl-4-methyl-pent-1-en (XXIe): A solution of XXd (10 mmol, 3.4 g) in absolute CCl_4 (25 ml) was stirred with N-chlorosuccinimid (18 mmol, 2.4 g) and 0.2 g α, α' -azobisobutyronitrile for 24 hrs. The succinimid formed was filtered off and the solvent removed *in vacuo* to yield XXIe. The product was purified by careful bulb to bulb distillation. Yield=3.0 g (81%) brownish yellow liquid, b.p. (bulb to bulb) (0.01 mm)=160°. Anal. Found: C, 71.75; H, 8.16; N, 3.82%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{30}\text{NClSi}$: C, 71.03; H, 8.13; N, 3.76%. IR (liquid): 2970, 1605, 1510, 1350, 1255, 865, 850 (broad), 750, 695. $^1\text{H}\delta$: two sets of signals indicating two isomers in the ratio 85:15 (min). 0.12 (min) and 0.21 [s, 9H, Si(CH₃)₃]; 0.9 (m, 6H, CH₃); 1.75-2.27 (m, 2H, CH); 2.90 (min and 3.12 (s, 3H, NCH₃); 6.4-6.8 (m, 3H) and 6.9-7.5 (m, 7H) aromatic. $^{13}\text{C}\delta$: -0.23 [q, Si(CH₃)₃]; 22.9 and 23.3 (q, diastereotopic, CH₃); 29.3 (d, CH); 38.3 (q, N-CH₃); 42.4 (d, CH-Si); 113.3 and 113.8 (min) (C_o, N-ph); 117.2 and 117.7 (min) (C_p, N-ph); signals at 127.6, 128.1, 128.8, 129.1 (d) and 137.9, 138.1, 139.3 (s) are crowded together and cannot be assigned; 147.3 (s, C_i, N-ph).

Preparation of XIIIb from IX: IX (10 mmol, 2.23 g) was deprotonated as described and quenched with trimethylsilylchloride, except that 1 hr after the addition of the chloride, a further quantity of *n*-butyllithium in *n*-hexane (11 mmol, 1.4 N) was added and the solution stirred for 3 hr (0°). After quenching with methyl iodide (12 mmol, 1.7 g) the mixture was stirred for 30 mins and allowed to warm up to rt. After following the work up procedure as described for XXa the raw product was dissolved in absolute CCl_4 (25 ml) and chlorinated as described for XXIa. To the crude product thus obtained, cooled in an icebath, trifluoroacetic acid (5 ml) was added and the mixture stirred at rt for 4 hrs. After addition of ether (30 ml) and HCl (20 ml, 4 N) the mixture was refluxed for 60 hrs. After shaking the mixture with methylene chloride (20 ml) and water (20 ml) the organic phase was washed twice with water (20 ml). Solid KOH (1 g) was added to the organic phase very carefully. After stirring for 2 hrs, the organic phase was washed again with water (30 ml) and the solvent removed *in vacuo*. NaF (1 g) and ethylalcohol (40 ml, 95%) were added to the residue and the mixture refluxed for 16 hrs. After cooling and filtering the alcohol solution was dried with anhydrous potassium carbonate and the alcohol removed under vacuum. Yield: 1.2 g (82%, GC-purity 66%), pale yellow liquid. b.p. (bulb to bulb) (0.01 mm)=70°.

Preparation of XIIIc from IX: With ethyl iodide analogous to XIII b. Refluxing time with HCl 86 hrs and with NaF 20 hrs. Yield: 1.4 g (87%, GC-purity 63%).

XXII and XXIII from IX: With isopropyl bromide analogous to XIII b. Refluxing time with HCl 92 hrs and with NaF 20 hrs. Yield: 1.3 g (mixture of products). Colourless liquid b.p. (bulb to bulb) (0.01 mm)=175°. Out of this distillate XXII (Glc-concentration 24%) and XXIII (Glc-concentration 42%) were isolated with the help of Glc and characterized.

1-Phenyl-3-(trimethylsilyl)-4-methyl-pentan-1-on XXII: Colourless liquid. Anal. Found: C, 72.49; H, 9.79%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{24}\text{OSi}$: C, 72.52; H, 9.74%. $^1\text{H}\delta$: 0.05 [s, 9H, Si(CH₃)₃]; 0.88 and 0.92 (d, J=7Hz, diastereotopic isopropyl CH₃, together 6H); 1.54-1.7 (m, 1H, H-C-Si); 1.81-2.21 [m, 1H, H-C-(CH₂)₂]; 3.01 (centre of ABX, m, J_{AB}=17 Hz, 2H, CH₂); 7.2-7.5 (m, 3H) and 7.7-7.9 (m, 2H) aromatic. $^{13}\text{C}\delta$: -0.9 (q, Si-CH₃); 21.4 and 22.8 (q, diastereotopic isopropyl CH₃); 28.3 and 29.0 (d, HC); 36.0 (+, CH₂); 128.1 (d, C_o); 128.6 (d, C_m); 132.7 (d, C_p); 137.4 (s, C_i); 201.0 (s, C=O).

1-Phenyl-2-chloro-4-methyl-pentan-1-on XXIII: Colourless liquid. $^1\text{H}\delta$: 1.02 (d, br, 6H, isopropyl); 1.51-2.25 [m, 3H, H-C-(CH₂)₂ and CH₂]; 5.10 (t, J=7 Hz, 1H, H-C-Cl) 7.2-8.0 (m, 5H arom.). $^{13}\text{C}\delta$: 21.6 and 22.9 (q, diastereotopic isopropyl CH₃); 25.3 [d, H-C-(CH₂)₂]; 42.2 (t, CH₂); 56.1 (d, H-C-Cl); 128.8 (d, C_o/C_m); 133.7 (d, C_p); 134.6 (s, C_i); 193.7 (C=O).

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References

- C. S. SUDHENDRANATH, Diplomarbeit, Justus Liebig-Universität Giessen, 1978 and partly Dissertation (in preparation).
- E. J. COREY, B. W. ERICKSON and R. NOYORI, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1971, 93, 1724.
- T. COHEN, D. A. BENNETT and A. J. MURA, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1976, 41, 2506.
- a) T. NAKAI, H. SHONO and M. OKAWARA, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1974, 3625.
b) T. NAKAI, H. SHONO and M. OKAWARA, *Chemistry Letters*, 1975, 249.
- T. HAYASHI and H. MIDORIKAWA, *Synthesis*, 1975, 100; I. HORI, T. HAYASHI and H. MIDORIKAWA, *Synthesis*, 1975, 727.
- M. WADA, H. NAKAMURA, T. TAGUCHI and H. TAKEI, *Chemistry Letters*, 1977, 345.
- E. PIERS and H. E. MORTON, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1979, 44, 3437.
- B. CORBEL, J.-P. PAUGAM, M. DREUX and P. SAVIGNAC, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1976, 835.
- J. C. CLINET and G. LINSTRUMELLE, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1978, 1137.
- I. KUWAJIMA and M. KATO, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1980, 623.
- a) H. J. REICH and S. K. SHAH, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 99, 263.
b) H. J. REICH, P. M. GOLD and F. CHOW, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1979, 4433.
- K. KONDO and D. TUNEMOTO, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1975, 1007.
- M. JULIA and B. BADET, *Bull. Soc. Chim. France*, 1975, 1363.
- P. C. CONRAD and P. L. FUCHS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 100, 346.
- G. K. COOPER and L. J. DOLBY, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1979, 44, 3414.
- A. DEBAL, T. CUVIGNY and M. LARCHEVEQUE, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1977, 3187.
- P. BAKUZIS, L. F. BAKUZIS and T. F. WEINGARTNER, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1978, 2371.
- a) H. J. CRISTAU, J.-P. VORS and H. CHRISTOL, *Synthesis*, 1979, 539.

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18. b) H. J. CRISTAU, J.-P. VORS and H. CHRISTOL, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1979, 2377.
19. D. CAINE and A. S. FROBES, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1978, 883, 5167.
20. H. AHLBRECHT and G. RAUCHSCHWALBE, *Synthesis*, 1973, 417.
21. G. RAUCHSCHWALBE and H. AHLBRECHT, *Synthesis*, 1974, 663.
22. H. AHLBRECHT and J. EICHLER, *Synthesis*, 1974, 672.
23. H. AHLBRECHT, *Chimia.*, 1977, 31, 391.
24. B. M. TROST and T. N. SALZMANN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 95, 6840.
25. I. PATERSON and I. FLEMING, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1979, 993, 995; T. SHONO, I. NISHIGUCHI, T. KOMAMURA and M. SASAKI, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 101, 984.
26. J. EICHLER, Dissertation, Justus Liebig-Universität, Giessen, 1976.
27. I. FLEMING and J. GOLDHILL, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. I.*, 1980, 1493.
28. K. REUCKER, Dissertation, Justus Liebig-Universität, Giessen, 1977.
29. G. RAUCHSCHWALBE, Dissertation, Justus Liebig-Universität, Giessen, 1974.
30. H. AHLBRECHT, J. BLECHER and F. KRÖHNKE, *Tetrahedron*, 1971, 27, 2169.
31. V. L. TWEEDIE and J. C. ALLABASHI, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 26, 3676.